

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Case Study

Panchkarma Therapy In The Management Of “Raktagata Vata” (Essential Hypertension) – A Case Study

Pooja K. Dhakar*, Gyan Prakash Sharma

Department of Panchakarma, PGIA Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India, Pin-code 342037

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12 Feb 2024

Accepted: 16 Feb 2024

Published: 21 Feb 2024

Keywords:

Hypertension, Panchkarma,
Management

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.10688917

ABSTRACT

Hypertension is one of the most common lifestyle disease today. Hypertension or high blood pressure is an asymptomatic medical condition in which systemic arterial blood pressure elevates beyond the normal value (more than 140/90mm of hg). It is also called a silent killer disease because most sufferers (85%) are asymptomatic and as per available reports, in more than 95% of cases of hypertension, underlying cause is not found. A 60-year old female patient presented with symptoms of Headache, Insomnia, Palpitation and Irregular bowel habit associated with 142/90mmhg Blood pressure. In fact, the incidence of hypertension is still rising alarmingly; there is a dire need to search for an effective and safe treatment because of the lack of current therapies to either provide a complete cure. Here Panchakarma procedures like Shirodhara is mentioned in the treatment of Essential Hypertension. An attempt has been made to assess the role of Takra dhara (Shirodhara) followed by Shiroabhyanga in managing Essential Hypertension in this case study. The total duration of the treatment was done for 14 days and follow-up was done on 7th day after completion of treatment. Improvement was assessed based on relief in the symptoms, subjective and objective parameters. Complete relief in all symptoms was noted after completion of the treatment. Any complications or adverse events due to treatment were not observed during the treatment period. This case report demonstrates the effectiveness of Takra Shirodhara in managing Essential Hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

High blood pressure is a common condition that affects the body's arteries. Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure, is a long-term medical condition in which the blood pressure in the arteries is persistently elevated¹. In high blood

pressure, the force of the blood pushing against the artery walls is consistently too high. The heart has to work harder to pump blood. About 90–95% of cases are primary (Essential Hypertension), defined as high blood pressure due to nonspecific

***Corresponding Author:** Pooja K. Dhakar

Address: Department of Panchakarma, PGIA Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India, Pin-code 342037

Email ✉: poojadhakar623@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

lifestyle and genetic factors. Lifestyle factors that increase the risk include excess salt in the diet, excess body weight, smoking, physical inactivity and alcohol use^{2,3}. Hypertension (persistent raised arterial pressure) Although, the handy literature is not observed in Ayurvedic classics, a review of previous theoretical and clinical works on this topic point out certain modes of involvement of dosha and dushya in the genesis of it. Most of the efforts show a prime role of Vata in the association of the remaining dosha pitta and Kapha. Also Acharya charaka permits to treat such disease without nomenclature by judging the involvement of dosha only⁴. Tridosha Vata - Pitta – Kapha and Dushya Rasa, Rakta play an important role in the pathogenesis of Hypertension and arteries are the main site of the disease. Symptoms like Shirahshoola (headache), Bhrama (giddiness), Hridravatva (palpitation), Anidra (insomnia), Vibandha (constipation) etc. are generally found in essential hypertension.

Material and Method

The patients was selected and registered for case study after their fulfillment of diagnostic criteria of Raktagata Vata (Essential Hypertension). The literary method is selected from Different Ayurvedic Literatures like Sushruta Samhita, Charak Samhita evam Astang Hridaya, Ayurvedic journals and internet.

CASE REPORT:

Patient Information

A female patient of age 60 year diagnosed with Raktagata Vata (Essential Hypertension) On the basis of CRF Presented in Out Patient Department (OPD) of PG Department of Panchkarma, University Hospital of Ayurved, Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan Rajasthan Ayurved University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India (OPD Registration Number- 18692) with complaints of Headache, Insomnia, Palpitation and Irregular bowel habit associated with 142/90mmhg Blood pressure. The onset of disease was started before 4.5 year. The

symptoms were initially mild, but their severity increased gradually. Patient took allopathy treatment i.e NSAID's, Atenolol for 2 years but did not get relief. Taking details about his daily routine, the patient has a sedentary-lifestyle irregular sleeping patterns, and dietary habits.

On Examination; General Examination

BP	142/90 mm Hg
PR	112/ minute
RR	14/ minute
Temp	35.8°C

Personal History:

Appetite	Decreases and vegetarian
Micturition	5-6 times/day, Normal
Sleep	Disturbed Sleep
Bowel	Constipation

Asthavidha Pariksha

Nadi	Vata-Kaphaj & 112/minute, regular	Shabda	Spashta(Clear)
Mala	Prakrit	Sparsha	Samsheetoshna
Mutra	Prakrit	Drika	Prakrit
Jivha	Mala aavrit	Aakriti	Sthool

Weight- 73.5 Kg

CNS- Patients is conscious, well oriented to time, place and person.

No relevant History of Past illness contributing to the current condition of the Patient.

No History of Diabetes Mellitus.

Family History: Present

Diagnostic Assessment

- Diagnosis of Hypertension is mainly Objective, which is based on elevated level of Sphygmomanometer reading.
- Sign and symptoms of the Raktagata Vata (Essential Hypertension).

SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

1. Severity scoring of Shiroshool (Headache)
2. Severity scoring of Bhrama (Giddiness)
3. Severity scoring of Klama (Fatigue)
4. Severity scoring of Hritspandan (Palpitation)

5. Severity scoring of Swedadhikyata (Excessive sweating)
6. Severity scoring of Anidra (Insomnia)

Therapeutic Intervention

According to predominance of Dosha Dushya and as per treatment mentioned in Ayurvedic Texts for Raktagata Vata, Takra Shirodhara along With Shiroabhyanga is selected for management. The total duration of the treatment was done for 14 days and follow-up was done 7th day after completion of treatment. Advises related to Pathya-Apathya (wholesome-unwholesome diet) were given during the treatment and follow-up period.

Table 1: Panchakarma Procedure timeline

Duration	Details of Procedure
14 Days:- 1 sittings (28 March 2023 – 10 April 2023)	Shiroabhyanga is done for 15 minute with Ksheerbala Taila. Dose- 15 ml After that Takra Shirodhara. Dose- 2 liter

Method of Takra Shirodhara (Relaxing Therapy)

It is carried out in three steps- Poorva karma, Pradhana Karma and Pashchat Karma.

A. Poorva karma

Shiro-abhayanga (Head massage): Then advice the patient to lie down on Droni (table). Apply lukewarm Ksheerbala Taila on head then massages the whole head, moving the palmar surface of the hand from before backwards applying gentle as well as firm pressure. Shiroabhyanga should be done on scalp, forehead, and neck for 15 minutes. After that prepare patient for Shirodhara.

B. Pradhana Karma

The patient should be lie down in supine position with ease on Droni (Shirodhara table). After Covering of Eye and Adjustment of Dhara Patra pouring of lukewarm medicated liquids over the forehead in a continuous manner from a four angula or 8 cm above the forehead of patient for 45 minutes.

C. Paschat karma

Head of the patient is wiped off, cleaned well and covered with towel. The patient is advised to take rest for short duration (10-15 minutes) followed by bath with lukewarm water.

FOLLOW-UP AND OUTCOMES

Follow-up was taken on 7th day after completion of treatment, during which clinical assessment was done based on the improvement of the patient's symptoms. No complications, new symptoms, or adverse events were observed during the entire treatment and follow-up period.

RESULTS

Sphygmomanometer reading before treatment is 140/90mmhg and after treatment is 125/68mmhg. Also there is improvement in the sign and symptoms of disease.

Table no 2 . Shows the Subjective Parameters before and after treatment with follow up

Subjective Parameters	Before treatment	After treatment	After follow up
Shiroshool (Headache)	2	1	1
Bhrama (Giddiness)	1	1	0
Klama (Fatigue)	3	2	2
Hritspandan (Palpitation)	4	3	2
Swedadhikyata (Excessive sweating)	0	0	0
Anidra (Insomnia)	4	2	1

DISCUSSION:

Shiro-abhyanga-

Acharya Charaka has defined Snehana as the treatment, which produces viscosity, softness, solubility and Kleda in the body (Cha.Su.22/10). Acharya Dalhana explains that when Sneha drug reaches to particular Dhatu then subsides the disease of that particular Dhatu⁵. Acharya Charaka has mentioned that Vayu dominates in the Sparshana Indriya and its Adhishtana is Twacha (skin)⁶. Indriya and mind automatically remains healthy as they are in close contact with each

other. Thus, Abhyanga keeps body and mind healthy⁷. Abhyanga has effect on skin, which is the seat for both Vata and Lasika. During Shiroabhyanga different type of mechanical sensation is given to the skin like pressure, rubbing, touches etc. so these sensory impulses are received by respective receptors present on the surface of the skin and carried to hypothalamus in the brain⁸. In Essential hypertension patient have headache, insomnia and stress related problems like anxiety, depression, irritability. Shiroabhyanga improves the blood circulation to the upper body parts, it cures headache, anxiety, depression, irritability and insomnia.

Probable mode of action of ksheerbala taila⁹-

The probable mode of action of Ksheerbala could be analyzed by its rasa panchaka. All three ingredients Bala, Ksheer and Tila Taila. Bala- Guru, Snigdha, Picchila, Madhura Vipaka, Sita Virya, Dosha karma Vata-pittashamka And Tila taila - Guru, Snigdha Madhura Vipaka, Ushana Virya, Dosha karma Tridosasamaka And Ksheer- Snigdha, Sita Virya, Dosha Karma Vata-pittanashaka. Ushana virya of taila taila reduces the vata and kapha. Since it has gone through processing by sheeta virya like Bala and ksheer, Its ushnatva may get altered.

Takra shirodhara-

Snehana is one among the Shadvidhopakramas. Pouring of a liquid on the forehead is known as Shirodhara, it can be done by different medicaments like Taila (oil), Takra (buttermilk), Kshira (milk), Kwatha(decoction), etc. In hypertension the Rakta dhatu or blood element is abruptly handled by the disturbed Vayu. The blood and Pitta have an inseparable relationship as Pitta resides in the blood. When the pitta gets disturbed, the Rakta too gets disturbed and vice versa. Takra dhara by the virtue of its sheeta effect pacifies the Ushana effect, intense and penetrating nature of both Pitta and Rakta. It also controls Vayu by the virtue of its combination. In this study we used medicated Takra for Shirodhara and it reduced both systolic and diastolic blood pressure of the patients of essential hypertension. In addition, it also provided significant relief in their symptoms like Shiroruk, Bhrama, Klama, Hrutspandan and Insomnia. The soothing of these Marma's and in turn soothing of Nervous system and endocrine glands as an effect of

Takra Dhara will definitely relax Prana Vayu, Sadhaka Pitta and Tarpaka Kapha in the brain (head). These inturn will have a relaxing effect over the Vyana Vayu, Ranjaka Pitta, Avalambaka Kapha and Udana Vayu controlling the heart functions and circulation. The ultimate effect will be a good relief from Hypertension. The Takra (buttermilk) has Ushana effect. But the combination of Musta and Takra produces a Sheeta effect on the brain and the whole nervous system and hence releases the stress and anxiety stagnant in the chief controlling station of our body. Takradhara stimulates it by its penetrating effect, which decreases the brain cortisones and adrenalin level. By Takradhara, patient feels relaxation, both physically and mentally. Relaxation of the frontalis muscle tends to normalize the entire body activity and achieves a decrease activity of sympathetic nervous system with lowering of heart rate, respiration, oxygen consumption, blood pressure, brain cortisones and adrenalin levels, muscle tension and probably increase in alpha brain waves. It strengthens the mind and spirit and this continues even after the relaxation. Corresponding to different levels and powers of consciousness there are nerve plexus and glands in human organisms. Special stimulation of different nerve plexus, glands and brain cells accompanies mental functions of different levels.

CONCLUSION:

Essential hypertension is a multifactorial cardiovascular disorder occurring particularly at middle and senile age. Both drugs, Ksheerbala taila Shiroabhyanga and Takra Shirodhara were found effective in reducing the systolic and diastolic blood pressure and also alleviating the symptoms of essential hypertension. No antagonist impact of the study drug was observed during the study. Based on the various observation and results acquired after finishing of the current research work, it can be concluded that, Ksheerbala taila Shiroabhyanga and Takra Shirodhara may be used in the management of Raktagata Vata (Essential hypertension). The clinical response regarding improvement in blood pressure and several symptoms of essential hypertension was milder in both panchkarma therapies. Ksheerbala taila Shiroabhyanga and Takra dhara combination is a safe and effective in

the management of Raktagata Vata (Essential Hypertension).

REFERENCES

1. CNaish j, Court DS(2014). Medical science (2 ed.). Elsevire Health Sciences. p. 526. ISBN9780702052491
2. Poulter NR, Prabhakaran D, Caulfield M(August 2015). "Hypertension". *Lancet*. 386(9995): 801-812
3. Carretero OA, Oparil S (January 2000). "Essential hypertension.Part 1:definition and etiology". *Circulation*. 101 (3): 329 -335.
4. Charaksmhita, Vidyotini Hindi commentary Chaukhamba Bharti Akadmi Prakashana Varansi, vol.1, Sutra Sthana chapter 20/44 page no. 383.
5. KV Krishna Das, text book of Medicine, pub. Jaypee brothers medical publisher(p)ltd [the health science publisher, new delhi/ london/ panama], vol. 2, 6th edition 2017 page no. 883
6. Sahasrayogam, Dr. K. Nishteswar, Dr. R. Vidyanath, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series office, varanasi, Second edition 2008, Taila Prakaran 3, page no. 110-111.
7. Charaka Smhita, Vidyotini Hindi commentary Chaukhamba Bharti Akadmi Prakashana Varansi, vol.1, Sutra Sthana chapter 22/10page no.424
8. Charaka Samhita by Agnivesha, Revised by Charaka and Dridhabala 'Vidyotini' Hindi commentary Part I (Reprint year 2012) Chaukhamba Bharati Academy, Varanasi, by Prof. Kashinath Shastri and Dr. Gorakhnath Chaturvedi, Sutra sthana chapter 17/12
9. Sahasrayogam, Dr. K. Nishteswar, Dr. R. Vidyanath, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series office, varanasi, Second edition 2008, Taila Prakaran 3, page no. 110-111.

HOW TO CITE: Pooja K. Dhakar, Gyan Prakash Sharma, Panchkarma Therapy In The Management Of "Raktagata Vata" (Essential Hypertension) – A Case Study, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 2, 597-601. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10688917>

